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Efficacy of metaldehyde in controlling *Theba pisana* (Gastropoda: Helicidae) snail on citrus orchards in Egypt: Effect of time, frequency and method of application

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Abstract

The effect of timing application, frequency, and application methods of metaldehyde was evaluated against *Theba pisana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) snail under field conditions. The results showed that when the application was repeated three times in three different months, the general mean of reduction percentage for *T. pisana* snail was higher than when it was repeated twice. A single application gave the lowest reduction percentage, and this was for both application methods (Hand sowing and on plastic pieces). As for the application time, the results showed the highest reduction percentage recorded in November, following January, while March recorded the lowest reduction percentage for the two application methods. Comparing the two application methods, the reduction percentage using hand sowing was higher than when using plastic pieces. By studying the population density before application, the highest snail count was in March in areas where the pesticide was not applied at all, followed by January, and November was the lowest. However, in areas where the pesticide was applied, the opposite of the previous results was observed, with March being the lowest. Therefore, it can be noted that pesticides are applied repeatedly in cases of high infestation to achieve the highest reduction percentage. It is preferable to carry out the control process in early November when the population is lower, and the hand-sowing method was the preferred method for controlling *T. pisana* snails.

Introduction

Terrestrial gastropods are a significant economic pest worldwide, including in Egypt. These snails and slugs infest plants at all growth stages, reducing yields and damaging edible parts of crops, fruits, and vegetables (Baur and Baur, 1993). *T. pisana* is a particularly widespread snail. Its distribution includes the entire

Mediterranean region and the Atlantic coast from Morocco to England (Yildirim and Gumus, 2004). It has also been introduced to Australia, South Africa, Brazil, Argentina, and parts of the United States, such as San Diego, Los Angeles, and California. It has been recorded in several Governorates across Egypt, including Beheira (Eshra, 2013), Kafr El-Sheikh (Heiba *et al.*, 2018),

Monufia (Heikal, 2015), Qalyubia, Sharkia, Gharbia, Damietta, Ismailia (Mohammed, 2015), Borg El Arab, and King Mariout Alexandria (Ali, 2017 and Bayoumi *et al.*, 2024), causing several damages to citrus orchards. *T. pisana* snails lay eggs in the soil, creating 3-4 cm deep holes and sealing them with a mixture of slime and soil. Each pair of snails can lay up to five clutches, with each snail producing around 120 eggs per season (Baker, 1986). Sacchi (1990) further investigated the life cycle of *T. pisana* and found that it can be either annual or biennial, depending on regional and local climatic conditions. Under laboratory conditions, Heikal (2015) found that the life cycles of *T. pisana* reach 313.3 ± 10.2 days with a mean of 25 ± 1.2 eggs per clutch.

The molluscicidal properties of metaldehyde were discovered in the 1930s in South Africa, at which point the chemical was being sold as fuel tablets (Gimingham, 1940). Within four years, it became the most popular control method for use against terrestrial gastropod pests in countries such as the UK. It was estimated that metaldehyde was used on 55% of the

crop areas where chemicals were being used against terrestrial gastropods (Garthwaite and Thomas, 1996). Metaldehyde is typically applied to land during the autumn and winter months when mollusks are most active due to the wet weather (Green, 1996). However, when overused, chemicals can be toxic to non-target organisms and can accumulate in the environment. In Egypt, many studies have studied the effect of metaldehyde on land snails, such as Abd El-Aal and Hamed (2010) and Abobakr *et al.* (2021).

The primary goal of this study is to determine the most effective method and timing for applying metaldehyde pesticide in the field. Additionally, the research aims to investigate whether repeated applications are necessary to reduce snail populations or if they simply contribute to environmental pollution.

Materials and methods

1. Origin of chemical:

Gastrotox (Metaldehyde pellet 5%), the chemical product tested in the trial, was obtained from the Central Laboratory for Pesticides, Agricultural Research Center.

Chemical structure of metaldehyde

2. Tested area:

The trial was conducted in flooded irrigated citrus orchards located in Minyat El-Qamh district, Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. The study period spanned from November 2024 to April 2025. The study area was divided into 2 zones (for hand sowing and for the application of plastic pieces). Each zone

is divided into six plots, each one containing five navel orange (*Citrus sinensis*) trees. Three plots for treatment, and the other acts as a buffer zone. In addition, another zone between the previous two zones containing one plot (Also five trees), without treatment, was used as a control.

3. Treatments:

The study utilized Gastrotox pesticide at a rate of 4 kg per feddan, employing two distinct application methods.

3.1. Application methods:

3.1.1. On plastic pieces:

This approach involved placing the bait on plastic pieces positioned beneath the trees.

3.1.2. Hand sowing:

In this method, the pesticide granules were dispersed over a one-meter by one-meter area surrounding each tree.

3.2. Application timeline:

The pesticide was applied on three separate occasions using both methods:

3.2.1. First application:

The initial application occurred in November 2024, followed by subsequent applications in January 2025 and March 2025. The reduction percentage was calculated after each application for both methods.

3.2.2. Second application:

Both methods were again applied in January 2025 and repeated in March 2025, with reduction percentages calculated after each application.

3.2.3. Third application:

The final application took place in March 2025, utilizing the same two methods, with reduction percentages calculated post-application. Taking into account that each application was repeated in the same private plot in an applied manner

4. Data collection:

4.1. Snail counts:

Alive and dead snails were counted before and after each treatment at 1, 3, 7, 14, and 21 days.

4.2. Reduction calculation:

Reduction percentages were calculated using the Henderson-Tilton equation (1955).

5. Statistical analysis:

The data obtained was subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Costat Statistical Software, (2005). The Least Significant Difference (LSD) test was performed at a significance level of $p \leq 0.05$.

Results and discussion

The effect of repeated application and application time of metaldehyde on the reduction percentage of *T. pisana* snails was evaluated under field conditions.

1. Impact of repeated metaldehyde applications on *Theba pisana* snail applied by hand sowing technique:

1.1. Repeated application:

Data in Table (1) revealed that the highest initial killing was consistently observed with three-time applications, specifically when applied in March (44.92%), followed by January (40.87%) and November (38.70%). The lowest initial killing effect was recorded for the one-time application in March (25.84%). In respect to the maximum residual killing percentage, it was also obtained with three-time applications, with the March application again being the most effective (88.29%), followed by January (84.61%) and November (82.88%). The lowest residual effect was associated with the one-time application in March (78.57%). Generally, it can be said that when metaldehyde was applied three times, the general mean of reduction percentage was higher than when it was applied twice, and a single application resulted in the lowest general mean of reduction percentage.

Table (1): reduction percentage of metaldehyde against *Theba pisana* snail by using the hand sowing technique.

Number of times of application	Method of application	Application time	Reduction percentage after indicated days							General mean
			Initial killing%			Residual killing%				
			1	3	Mean	7	14	21	Mean	
Three time	Hand sowing	November	22.59bc	54.81a	38.70b	72.80ab	90.34bc	85.50bc	82.88b	65.20c
		January	23.68b	58.07a	40.87b	73.30ab	92.25ab	88.27b	84.61b	67.11b
		March	32.76a	57.09a	44.92a	75.59a	95.78a	93.50a	88.29a	70.94a
Two time	Hand sowing	January	22.06bc	30.74c	26.40d	64.53d	89.70bc	85.43bc	79.89c	58.49e
		March	19.64cd	44.62b	32.13c	70.57bc	91.14b	86.72bc	82.81b	62.54d
One time	Hand sowing	March	17.55d	34.14c	25.84d	67.07cd	86.39c	82.25c	78.57c	57.48e
LSD at 0.05 =			3.56	4.09	2.76	3.53	4.13	4.47	2.21	1.74
P value =			.0000***	.0000***	.0000***	.0000***	.0036**	.0009***	.0000***	.0000***

1.2. Application time:

As shown in Table (1), the results indicated that when considering the effect of time alone, it had a significant impact on the reduction percentage. The highest initial effect (38.70%) was observed in November, followed by January (26.40%), while March showed the lowest reduction percentage (25.84%). The same pattern was observed for the residual effect; the ranking of the reduction percentage was similar to that for the initial effect, with November and January showing the highest reduction percentage (82.88% and 79.89%), respectively, while March had the lowest reduction percentage (78.57%). General mean reduction percentages were 65.20, 58.49, and 57.48% for November, January, and

March, respectively. Data in Figure (1) showed a significant difference in the number of snails, with the highest number (58.2) recorded in March in the area where no snail control had been applied in the previous months. The lowest number of snails (8.4) was recorded in March in the area where the pesticide was applied twice, in November and the following January. No significant differences were found in the number during November and January in the areas where the pesticide had not been used, and in March in the area where the pesticide had been applied once, in January. In general, applying pesticides in November and January significantly reduces the population before applying them in March.

Figure (1): Population density of *Theba pisana* snail prior to application of metaldehyde by using the hand sowing method technique.

2. Impact of repeated metaldehyde applications on *Theba pisana* snails applied by putting on plastic piece technique:

2.1. Repeated application:

Data from Table (2) showed that three-time applications give the highest reduction percentage for both initial and residual effects, compared to two-time or single applications. The maximum initial killing reduction percentage was recorded with the three-time application

in March (36.26%), followed by January (34.43%). The lowest initial killing was recorded for the one-time application in March (23.31%). Similarly, the maximum residual killing percentage was obtained with three-time applications, with March (83.82%) again being the most effective, followed by January (80.33%) and November (79.33%). The lowest residual effect was recorded with the one-time application in March (72.25%).

Table (2): Reduction percentage of metaldehyde against *Theba pisana* snail by using the plastic pieces technique.

Number of times of application	Method of application	Application time	Reduction percentage after indicated days							General mean
			Initial killing%			Residual killing%				
			1	3	Mean	7	14	21	Mean	
Three time	On plastic pieces	November	17.35c	44.54b	30.94b	74.42ab	81.19ab	82.36b	79.33b	59.97c
		January	20.39ab	48.48ab	34.43a	72.94b	83.47a	84.60b	80.33b	61.97b
		March	22.62a	49.91a	36.26a	77.88a	84.07a	89.51a	83.82a	64.79a
Two time	On plastic pieces	January	18.35bc	30.98c	24.66c	58.20d	78.51b	82.82b	73.18d	53.77d
		March	16.41c	45.68ab	31.04b	65.54c	80.44ab	83.94b	76.77c	58.48c
One time	On plastic pieces	March	15.71c	30.91c	23.31c	60.29d	71.05c	85.40b	72.25d	52.67d
LSD at 0.05 =			3.00	4.55	2.58	3.88	4.30	3.56	2.27	2.00
P value =			.0006***	.0000***	.0000***	.0000***	.0000***	.0052**	.0000***	.0000***

2.2. Application time:

When considering the time of application alone, the results indicated a significant impact on the reduction percentage, with a clear ranking for both initial and residual effects. November showed the highest initial killing (30.94%), followed by January (24.66%), while March exhibited the

lowest (23.31%). The ranking for residual effect mirrored the initial effect, with November (79.33%) and January (73.18%) showing the highest reduction percentages and March showing the lowest (72.25%). Overall, the general mean reduction percentage ranked as November (59.97%), January (53.77%), and March (52.67%).

Figure (2): Population density of *Theba pisana* snail prior to application of metaldehyde using the plastic piece methods.

Data from Figure (2) showed a significant difference in the number of *T. pisana* snails, with the highest number of 57 recorded in March in the area where no control was applied during the previous months. The lowest number of snails was recorded in March in the area where the pesticide was applied twice, in November and the following January. No significant differences were found in the number of snails in January in the area where the pesticide was never used, nor in March in the area where the pesticide was applied once in January. There were significant differences in the first area where the pesticide was applied three times, with the numbers recorded as 34.2, 26.4, and 12.8 in November, January, and March, respectively. In general, applying pesticides in November and January significantly

reduces the number of *T. pisana* snails during March.

3. Impact of application method:

A comparison of the two application methods, as shown in Tables (1 and 2), revealed significant differences in their effectiveness, particularly in terms of the maximum reduction percentage. The Hand-sowing method, when applied three times in March, delivered the highest general mean reduction percentage (70.94%). Compared with application on plastic pieces, which gave (64.79%), the same trend was achieved with two-time application and one-time application. Generally, a difference in effectiveness was observed between the two methods, both in terms of application time and repeated application. The hand sowing application method was more effective than applying it to plastic pieces,

although the latter method was still effective.

It was obvious that the molluscicidal activity of metaldehyde differed from season to season, with noticeable reduction percentages during autumn and winter seasons, while the lowest one was noticed during the spring season. This may be attributed to the number of *T. pisana* being at a low level of infestation during autumn and winter months, then increasing to reach a high level of infestation in spring months. This is in harmony with Bayoumi *et al.* (2024) and Abed *et al.* (2025), who reported that the population density of *T. pisana* snails increased gradually after winter till reaching its maximum density in spring. For this reason, control methods at the beginning of the breeding season gave good control of these pests and reduced damage caused by them during winter, autumn, and spring seasons.

Concerning repeated control applications, it is a highly effective strategy for minimizing snail population density. This is attributed to the ability of such repeated treatments to eliminate a significant number of snails before and during their egg-laying season, thereby limiting the spread of population increases and the severity of future infestations. This strategy is critical because a single adult snail can lay numerous eggs, and killing the adults before oviposition prevents thousands of potential offspring from hatching. Specifically, the timing mentioned, where the egg-laying season begins in November and continues until March of the following year, is a crucial biological window. Therefore, repeating the control operation during this November-to-March breeding season is scientifically sound, as it directly reduces the next generation, thus lowering the overall infestation in future seasons (Heikal, 2015, and Bayoumi, 2024). As for the

method of application, the hand-sowing method is very effective, as is placing it on plastic pieces. This is due to the increased chance of metaldehyde reaching the snail during its movement, thus increasing the reduction percentage (Ismail *et al.*, 2016).

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